

GENDER-BASED VIOLENCE IN UNIVERSITIES AND RESEARCH ORGANISATIONS

NATIONAL FIELDWORK REPORT

Country: Austria

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Date: 10/05/2021

1. INTRODUCTION

Although equality between men and women is part of the Austrian constitution, gender equality is still far away from reality. In many parts of society, women continue to be discriminated against because of their gender.

The Austrian Federal Act on Protection Against Domestic Violence (“Bundesgesetz zum Schutz vor Gewalt in der Familie”) entered into force on 1 May 1997. After several amendments, the Second Act on Protection Against Violence (2009) was adopted, with further improvements regarding the protection of and support for violence victims. The latest amendment dates back to autumn 2013 and expands the protection of children affected by violence. The corresponding acts include protection by the police and under civil law, measures under criminal law as well as victims’ rights. Every person residing in Austria, regardless of origin or nationality, is entitled to protection against violence.

Despite this legal framework, it is a terrifying fact that annually approximately 20 to 30 women are victims of femicides. Most of these women are murdered by their partner or ex-partner. The year 2021 seems to set a negative record: Up to May 10, 12 women have become victims of femicides. The public debates on this tragedy are linked to the conservative attitude of “protect-your-daughters” rather than an “educate-your-sons” approach.

In Austria, government funding for activities to prevent and combat violence against women is made available at both the federal and the regional levels. The measures and activities that are publicly funded, in whole or in part, include the following: awareness-raising activities, research, networking meetings, NGO-run counselling and support services (in particular the nine violence protection centres across the country), perpetrator programs, and court assistance for victims of violent crime. In addition, several measures taken by public authorities in response to violence against women are funded, including the institution of one specifically trained domestic violence officer in each law enforcement unit, specialist prosecution services, and a national helpline for victims of violence against women.

In Austria, sexual harassment and GBV are regulated comprehensively through legal acts which range from the Federal Equal Treatment Act to the Criminal Code. Regarding universities and their legal framework, the fundamental law of Austrian university, the “University Act” includes the reference that universities should implement fundamental laws concerning equality, such as the “Equal Treatment Act”. However, especially when talking about harassment on a mental and

psychological level, Austria in general and the RPOs, in particular, are often representing an attitude of “Don’t be so sensible – I did not mean it that way.”

Regarding universities and other research-performing organisations, universities are considered quite progressive. Nevertheless, sexual harassment is happening in university settings, too. It should be noted that there do not exist any prevalence studies for the RPO sector in Austria, which would be able to show how many people are affected. GBV-related incidents usually happen when teachers and students are two by two: during consultation hours, exam insights or conference visits.

On the one hand, there are working groups for equal treatment issues in universities (which are regulated by the University Act 2002). The working groups for equal treatment issues function as counselling centres and also have the power to intervene.

The “Working Groups for Equal Treatment Issues” (“Arbeitskreis für Gleichbehandlungsfragen”) exist since the early 1990s. They are obligatory by law and assigned with more competencies by the UG amendment. It is easy to contact them as the homepages of the universities show the subpage ‘Working Group for Equal Treatment Issues’ (“Arbeitskreis für Gleichbehandlungsfragen”). Their duties are the following: Preventing discrimination by university governing bodies and equal opportunity issues regarding religion, gender, ideology, sexual orientation, age, etc. In cases of discrimination or sexual harassment, a complaint can be lodged with the equal opportunities working party, which can request a court of arbitration. Paragraph 42 Universitätsgesetz (University Act) provides the legal basis for equal opportunities working for parties.

Many staff members and students do not know of these institutions and their responsibilities.

Not every victim wants to report their case or is able to work up the courage that is required to leave anonymity and testify in court. Due to the fear of bad marks or lack of knowledge about counselling services, only a few victims decide to come forward.

There are two main national legal frameworks in place:

1. According to the Federal Equal Treatment Act (Bundes-Gleichbehandlungsgesetz B-GIBG), subsequent forms of discrimination are also forbidden
 - sexual harassment
 - gender-related harassment
 - harassment due to ethnicity, religion or ideology, age and sexual orientation
2. Criminal Code of the Republic of Austria (Strafgesetzbuch StGB): Sexual assaults such as (forcible) rape or other sexual acts, such as sexual harassment, public sexual acts, sexual coercion, stalking, bodily injury and abuse of authority, are regulated in further sections of the Criminal Code.

These frameworks also apply at universities. The Federal Equal Treatment Act (Bundes-Gleichbehandlungsgesetz B-GIBG) also offers university staff and students protection against

sexual harassment in the workplace. The sexual harassment must be made credible, and it is up to the alleged harasser to prove that no sexual harassment has taken place.

The Criminal Code (§ 218 StGB) does not cover verbal and non-verbal sexual harassment without physical contact, which is therefore not punishable by the courts. This applies to insinuating remarks and glances as well as sexist jokes, for example, yet these are never in order. However, these acts, if committed in the field of employment and training, may constitute discrimination on the grounds of sex and are then regulated under the provisions of the Equal Treatment Acts. The Equal Treatment Act defines sexual harassment as follows: “conduct belonging to the sexual sphere which affects the dignity of a person or is intended to do so and is unwanted, inappropriate or offensive to the person concerned”.

(Sexual) harassment, as well as mobbing, are violations that are included in the Civil Servant/Service Act (Beamten-Dienstrechtsgesetz) and can be punished by applying disciplinary law. Paragraph §43a says, "Civil servants and their employees shall treat each other with respect. Superiors, as well as employees, should therefore contribute to a good functioning of official cooperation. In dealing with their superiors, colleagues and employees, they shall refrain from creating working conditions that violate their human dignity, have the purpose of doing so or are otherwise discriminatory.”

2. MAPPING OF POLICIES AND LEGAL FRAMEWORKS

Policies and legal frameworks on a national level that tackle GBV in general without a specific reference to universities:

- Federal Act on Protection Against Domestic Violence (Bundesgesetz zum Schutz vor Gewalt in der Familie BGSchG)
- Federal Equal Treatment Act (Bundes-Gleichbehandlungsgesetz B-GIBG)
- Sexual harassment and public sexual acts § 218 Criminal Code (Strafgesetzbuch StGB)
- (Forcible) rape § 201 Criminal Code (Strafgesetzbuch StGB)
- Sexual coercion § 202 Criminal Code (Strafgesetzbuch StGB)
- Stalking § 107a Criminal Code (Strafgesetzbuch StGB)
- Bodily injury §§ 83 ff Criminal Code (Strafgesetzbuch StGB)
- Abuse of authority § 212 Criminal Code (Missbrauch eines Autoritätsverhältnisses § 212 Strafgesetzbuch StGB)
- Coercion § 105 Criminal Code (Nötigung § 105 Strafgesetzbuch StGB)

Policies and legal frameworks on the university level that tackle GBV to a certain extent:

- University Act (Universitätsgesetz 2002 UG)
- Civil Servants/Service Act (Beamten-Dienstrechtsgesetz 1979)
- All universities have a “Women’s Promotion Plan” and/or a “Gender Equality Plan” in place. As to the author’s knowledge, nearly all plans include GBV-issues, such as protection of dignity at work, including measures against sexual harassment, harassment and bullying. The precise definitions of these plans are under the responsibility of the universities.

Main actors/stakeholders (general):

- The “Ombud for Equal Treatment” is a governmental institution that is competent to enforce the right of equal treatment and equality and the right of protection against discrimination. It supports people in asserting their right to equal treatment and carries out advisory, informative, and awareness-raising activities that are based on the Equal Treatment Act. There is one Central Office in Vienna and 4 Regional offices in the provinces/federal states (“Bundesländer”) of Austria. Their advisory service and support are confidential and free of charge. <https://www.gleichbehandlungsanwaltschaft.gv.at/english/information-and-advice.html>
- Women’s counselling centres take a leading role in combatting GBV. Outside opening hours, the women’s helpline can be reached for initial and crisis counselling throughout Austria 24/7 at 0800 222 555 (free of charge).
- The Chamber of Labour represents employees towards politics and business, participates in discussions about legislation and offers support concerning labour law-related issues.
- Trade unions advise companies, works councils and individuals not only in matters of anti-discrimination and preventing violence but also in preventing violence and mobbing at the workplace, in the equal treatment and disability equality law, the employment of the elderly, the chronically ill and disabled people, as well as in gender mainstreaming and diversity management issues.

Main bodies/stakeholders at universities:

- The “Working Group for Equal Treatment Issues” (“Arbeitskreis für Gleichbehandlungsfragen”) is a body that exists by law at all public universities. It provides staff members (researchers and administration) as well as students and university bodies with information and support in matters of gender equality. Furthermore, topics such as equal treatment regardless of gender, ethnic affiliation, religion or ideology, age and sexual orientation are being addressed, as well as the promotion of women. Other tasks are: accompanying control of staffing procedures, admission procedures and appointment procedures; counteracting discrimination within the university; counselling and support in case of bullying or sexual harassment, gender harassment, ethnicity, religion or ideology, age, sexual orientation and further discrimination; information on equal treatment in language and gender mainstreaming. All Working Groups are granted special rights in the execution of their tasks. The members are independent, free from instructions and have to obey official secrecy.
- The “Works Council for Academic and Artistic Staff” (“Betriebsrat für das Wissenschaftliche und künstlerische Personal”) and the “Works Council for General Staff” (“Betriebsrat für das Allgemeine Universitätspersonal”) represent and preserve the interest of the mentioned parties with regard to the university management. They promote the economic, social, cultural and health interests of the employees and hold a supporting role when combatting GBV at universities.
- The “Student Union” (Österreichische HochschülerInnenschaft) acts as the legal representative of students’ interests at universities, private universities, universities of applied sciences and colleges of teacher education towards university

management and government. Student membership is compulsory. The Student Union, especially the groups dealing with feminist and/or gender equality issues, also conduct activities to combat GBV at universities. <https://www.oeh.ac.at/>

Additionally, some universities have an Ombudsperson's Office for Students.

Targeting their staff members, the RPO provide general information on GBV and offers support in terms of confidential consulting and support activities when cases of GBV arise. A brief screening of relevant curricula indicated that GBV is a topic in legal studies.

Legal Studies:

- The law faculty of the University of Vienna offers elective courses to obtain the Diploma of "Legal Gender Studies", which focuses on gender relations in the legal discourse. The Chair of Legal Gender Studies was also involved in the Feminist Lawyers' Day (Feministischer Juristinnentag), which took place in Vienna for the first time in 2016.
- The Johannes Kepler University in Linz also researches and teaches on these topics at the Institute for Legal Gender Studies. Students can thus specialise in legal gender studies, anti-discrimination and diversity.

Medicine:

- Since 2010, the Medical University of Vienna provides the postgraduate programme of "gender medicine", which is unique in Austria. The aim of this study programme is to acquire gender-specific knowledge and treatment methods and to teach gender-sensitive attitudes.
- The Medical University of Innsbruck offers a range of elective classes to enable students to deepen their knowledge of gender medicine and diversity.

In Austria, GBV is discussed on a general level and is mostly related to domestic violence. The universities rely on the general "Federal Equal Treatment Act" with its anti-discrimination legislation and its regulation against GBV. Universities have installed the "Working Group for Equal Treatment Issues" (by law) and provide services and information. Internal procedures on how and where victims can receive support and help are in place.

3. DEBATES REGARDING #METOO AND THE ISTANBUL CONVENTION

Provide a brief overview of any debates related to the #MeToo movement (or other similar/related movements if relevant) and the ratification of the Istanbul Convention, specifically in relation to universities and research organisations.

In a series of interviews conducted by the paper "Der Standard" one year after the rise of the #MeToo debate, approximately eight female and two male students were asked about changes the movement might have provoked. Many students were very positive about the fact that these issues are now discussed more openly and have become more prevalent in society as a result of #MeToo. By making them visible and dealing with abuses more openly, more women were able to work up the courage to share their experiences. The students also had the impression that due to the movement, further gender-related topics, such as inequality in payment, have been brought into focus.

In another article of "Der Standard", however, it was noted that the debate achieved only little in terms of improved victim protection. Although there has been a lively exchange on this topic, power relations have been criticised too little, women have been labelled as the "weak sex", and thus the goal of real equality (which should be supported by an adaption of social policies and legislation according to the author) has been missed.

In 2013, Austria ratified the Istanbul Convention. In 2016, Austria was among the first two countries to be evaluated by GREVIO (Group of Experts on Action against Violence against Women and Domestic Violence) regarding the implementation of the Istanbul Convention. Austrian civil society organisations and women's associations commented on the situation by a Shadow Report.

4. PUBLIC OPINION ON GBV

Current situation/news in Austria: Since 2014, femicides have more than doubled in Austria. After the number of femicides has increased steeply during the past years, a maximum number of 41 women were killed in 2018. In 2021, the numbers are most likely to be very high again, sadly - by the end of April. There had already been committed nine femicides in Austria. By May 10th, we are facing 12 victims. In most cases, the murderer was the partner or the ex-partner of the murdered woman. Worldwide, it is a sad certainty that women's homes are simultaneously their most dangerous places to be.

In Austria, calls for measures to combat violence against women have been growing ever louder during the past few weeks. Victim protection centres have already stated that they were working at their limits and often could not care adequately for women due to staffing or financial deficits. It is assumed that this problem is due to the current Covid-19 pandemic, which is said to have led to an increase in domestic violence, whereas at the same time, women have been deprived of opportunities to escape.

On May 3rd, 2021, the Austrian federal government, therefore, announced measures which should protect women from violence. The measures include an increase in police officers who have special training in the field of violence and prevention, an increase in case conferences and a better transfer of information in cases of stalking. In addition, future female judges and public prosecutors will be sensitised to these issues in their training. The awareness-raising campaign focusing on violence against women, which was already launched last year due to the pandemic, is now to be intensified.

It has to be stated that no public survey on GBV in general nor at the university level has been conducted so far in Austria.

5. IMPACT OF COVID-19 ON DISCUSSIONS ABOUT GBV

The impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on GBV has been discussed in Austria, mainly in the domestic context. No discussions concerning the impacts of COVID-19 on GBV at universities and research organisations have arisen so far.

6. CONCLUSION

As for Austria, baseline research on GBV in the field of RPOs and RFOs, as well as a public debate on the structural impacts of GBV, are highly needed. As is already highlighted in the GREVIO-report, Austrian authorities should take measures to monitor the prevalence of different forms of violence against women. RPOs, as these organisations are workplaces of many researchers, administrative staff members as well as students, should be tackled specifically. As for universities, safe spaces for FLIT*(Frauen/Women, Lesbian, Inter- and Trans-)-persons who are understood as places of retreat and places where advice and support are given should be provided. University bodies and the judiciary have to take clear action against the perpetrators. A long-term sensitisation on issues concerning GBV of the relevant people and decision-makers is highly required.

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101006261.

The contents of this publication are the sole responsibility of the Institute of Sociology of the Czech Academy of Sciences and do not necessarily reflect the opinion of the European Union.